

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Reaction Between Dihalodicarbonylrhodate(I) Anions and Pyridine

F. H. JUMEAN

Department of Chemistry, University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan

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The kinetics of the reaction between dihalodicarbonylrhodate(I) anions of the formula $[\text{RhX}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$, and pyridine was followed spectrophotometrically and the effect of temperature on the rate constants was investigated. The reaction was found to obey a second order rate expression, first order in each of the complex anion and pyridine. The rate constants follow the decreasing order $\text{I} > \text{Br} > \text{Cl}$. A mechanism is proposed to account for these observations.

THE 4-coordinate complexes of rhodium (I) are of the d^8 square planar type¹. They are noted for their ability to undergo oxidative addition reactions with a variety of ligands, leading to the formation of d^6 octahedral complexes². The carbonyl complexes of rhodium (I) are particularly interesting because of the Rh-CO bond. The strength of this bond, as indeed is the case for many other metal carbonyl bonds, is believed to originate from a synergetic effect produced by (i) the donation of the lone electron pair on CO to the metal, and (ii) the back donation of electrons from the non-bonding d orbitals of rhodium to the antibonding orbitals of CO³. The net effect is to strengthen the Rh-CO bond, conferring upon it a double bond character, and to reduce the bond order of CO in the complex. A verification of this effect is furnished by infrared spectral data⁴ which show sizable shifts in the stretching frequencies of Rh-CO and CO bonds. Thus, reactions involving the departure of such a metal liganded carbonyl proceed slowly because of the synergetic effect. The departure of a second liganded carbonyl would take place even more slowly because the d electrons on the metal would now be more available for the strengthening of the remaining metal-CO bond. In rhodium (III) complexes, however, the Rh-CO bond is much weaker than that in rhodium (I) complexes, because of the decreased availability of electrons for back donation.

The dihalodicarbonylrhodate (I) anion, $[\text{RhX}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$, has a cis square planar geometry⁴. When an ethanolic solution of this anion is reacted with pyridine (py) the product⁵ formed is the octahedral complex trihalotris (pyridine) rhodium(III). The infrared spectrum⁶ of this complex suggests that this product is a mixture of two isomers. In this work, the kinetics of this reaction, for all three halo analogues, was followed and the temperature effect, for the purpose of obtaining activation parameters, was investigated. The aim

is to postulate a mechanism which would answer the question as to whether the departure of CO occurs before or after the oxidation of Rh(I) to Rh(III), to determine at what stage in the course of the reaction does the addition of pyridine take place, and to shed some light on the role played by the halogen ligands.

Experimental

Materials: Rhodium trichloride was purchased in the hydrated form from Johnson Matthey Chemicals, Ltd., England. Carbon monoxide was generated by reacting formic acid with concentrated sulfuric acid. All other materials were of A.R. grade and were used without further purification.

Preparation of Compounds: The dichlorodicarbonylrhodium (I) anion, $[\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-$, was prepared by refluxing an ethanolic solution of hydrated rhodium trichloride (0.2 g in 30 ml) with carbon monoxide for about five hours with continuous stirring⁶. During this time the color changed from dark red to pale yellow. The bromo and iodo analogues were prepared by metathesis^{4,7}. The product in each case was isolated and purified according to the method described by Kingston *et al*⁵. Infrared spectra taken for the solutions agreed closely with literature values⁴.

Instrumentation: A Unicam SP 8000 spectrophotometer, fitted with a thermostated cell compartment, was employed for monitoring all reactions. The wavelength calibration was verified by taking a spectrum for holium oxide. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 grating spectrophotometer.

Rate measurements: The reaction rate for the chloro and bromo analogues with pyridine was followed at 350 nm and that for the iodo analogue

at 386 nm. All solutions were thermostated for at least 20 minutes prior to mixing. The reference cell in each case contained the solvent, absolute ethanol, to which was added the necessary amount of pyridine needed to make its concentration identical in both cells. For the purpose of studying the effect of temperature, measurements were made in the temperature interval 15-45°. For each individual run, the equilibrium absorbance value, A_e , was obtained either several hours after mixing or the following day.

Results

Absorbance values were obtained at 25.0° as a function of time for several ethanolic solutions containing equimolar concentrations of $[\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-$, ($5.10 \times 10^{-4} M$) and varying concentrations of pyridine (0.11-2.48 M). The linearity of the $\log(A_t - A_e)$ vs. time plots indicates that the reaction is first order with respect to time (A_t and A_e are the absorbance values at time t and at equilibrium, respectively). From the slope of each line, an apparent first order rate constant, k'_1 , was calculated. When the k'_1 values were plotted as a function of pyridine concentration, a fairly linear plot was obtained indicating that the reaction is first order with respect to pyridine. The reaction thus obeys a second order rate expression, first order with respect to each of pyridine and the complex anion. The observation that a pseudo-first order rate law is operative ought not to be surprising in view of the large stoichiometric excess of pyridine. The second order rate constant, k_2 , as calculated from the slope of this plot has the value of 1.93×10^{-2} liter mole $^{-1}$ min $^{-1}$.

The kinetic behaviour for the reactions of the bromo and iodo analogues with pyridine was investigated in the same manner and the rate law was found to be identical for all the three analogues. The second order rate constants for the bromo and iodo analogues were found to have the values of 4.10×10^{-2} and 9.95×10^{-2} litre mole $^{-1}$ min $^{-1}$ respectively.

In view of these results the empirical rate expression, satisfying all three reactions, may be written as

$$-\frac{d[\text{RhX}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-}{dt} = k'_1[\text{RhX}_2(\text{CO})_2]^- = k_2[\text{py}][\text{RhX}_2(\text{CO})_2]^- \quad \dots(1)$$

This rate expression was further verified by varying the concentration of the complex ion, for all three reactions, over an approximately tenfold range, while maintaining a constant initial concentration of pyridine (1.30 M). Plots of the initial rate vs. the concentration of the complex ion initially present were linear in each case, confirming that the reaction

is first order with respect to the complex ion. Furthermore, the slopes of these plots were fairly nearly identical with the k'_1 values expected at this concentration of pyridine.

Effect of temperature: The effect of temperature on the second order rate constant was investigated for all three reactions. The data were plotted according to the Eyring equation :

$$k_2 = (kT/h) \exp(\Delta\ddot{S}^*/R) \exp(\Delta\ddot{H}^*/RT) \quad \dots(2)$$

The activation parameters $\Delta\ddot{H}^*$ and $\Delta\ddot{S}^*$, as calculated from the slope and intercept of a plot $\ln(k_2/T)$ vs T respectively, are given in Table I.

TABLE - 1

X	$\Delta\ddot{H}^*$, kcal/mole	$\Delta\ddot{S}^*$, cal deg $^{-1}$ mole $^{-1}$
Cl	11.2	-37.0
Br	8.71	-43.7
I	6.23	-50.4

Discussion

The results of this investigation indicate that only one of the three pyridine molecules incorporated in the final product, $[\text{RhX}_3\text{Py}_3]$, is involved in the rate determining step. Now if the reaction were to follow a bimolecular displacement (SN_2) mechanism, with the approach of a pyridine molecule leading to the synchronous departure of a carbonyl, then the second order rate constants associated with the complex anions should be highest for the chloro, and lowest for the iodo, analogues. This is because the Rh-C bond order, as evidenced by infrared measurements⁴, is highest for the iodo, and lowest for the chloro, analogue. This is readily explained on the basis that the most electronegative halogen, chlorine in this case, would be most efficient in withdrawing electrons away from the Rh-C bond, thereby reducing its double bond character.

On the basis of the above argument, it may be concluded that the rate determining step does not involve the departure of a carbonyl group. This conclusion is further supported by two additional pieces of evidence : (i) The high negative $\Delta\ddot{S}^*$ values obtained in this work suggest a transition state more restricted than that encountered in typical SN_2 reactions. Since tetragonal pyramidal complexes of rhodium are known⁸, it seems reasonable to postulate this geometry for the activated complex, with a pyridine molecule occupying the apex. From these values, moreover, it may be concluded that the iodo analogue is associated with the most restricted transition state and hence the shortest Rh-py bond. (ii) Although no values for Rh-C bond energies in Rh (I) complexes are available, the

$\Delta \ddot{H}^*$ values obtained are quite lower than would be expected for a metal carbon bond with a partial double bond character. Furthermore, even if it is assumed that the $\Delta \ddot{H}^*$ values correspond to bond energies, this assumption falls apart because it would be inconsistent with the evidence⁴ that the Rh-C bond is strongest for the iodo, and weakest for the chloro, analogue.

On the other hand, electron rich central atoms should be more susceptible to the loss of an electron pair than their electron deficient counterparts. Since the electron density on rhodium in $[\text{RhX}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-$ would be highest for the iodo, and lowest for the chloro, analogue, i.e. opposite to the trend in electronegativity, it follows that the oxidation of Rh(I) to Rh(III) ought to be fastest for the iodo, and slowest for the chloro, analogue. This leads to the suggestion that the oxidation step is probably synchronous with the addition of the first pyridine molecule. This seems more plausible when considering that the tetragonal pyramidal geometry proposed in this work is normally associated with Rh(III) rather than Rh(I) complexes¹.

The above arguments lead to the postulation of the following mechanism :

2 Octahedral isomers

It may be noted that the second (fast) step probably involves two fast steps, one for the removal of each carbonyl group.

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